

Comparison of the Organs at Risk's doses in Pelvic Radiotherapy, version 2

Jeno Palvolgyi

Abstract

The study aimed to evaluate Prostate, Bladder, Gynec, and Anal canal cancer VMAT radiotherapy plans using different protocols.

Introduction

The radiotherapy (RT) plans are prepared to fulfill the requirements for dose coverage and inhomogeneity of the PTVs, simultaneously satisfying the dose limits of the organs at risk (OAR). The RT protocol instructions and constraints differ from prescription dose, fraction dose, dose constraints of the OARs, and the number of checked DVH graph points, which are single or multiple. The acceptance levels are: PASS/FAIL, OPTIMAL /GOOD / ACCEPTABLE, and PER-PROTOCOL/ VARIATION ACCEPTABLE.

The study aimed to evaluate Prostate, Bladder, Gynec, and Anal canal cancer VMAT RT plans prepared using local protocols, and with other protocols.

Materials and Methods

1. Five prostate cancer plans were prepared using the local protocol with 44Gy + two 16 Gy and 14 Gy sequential boosts, and five other plans with 60Gy + 14Gy boost. They were evaluated using the PROKNOW systems protocol instructions applicable to a 60 Gy dose prescription [1].
2. Five bladder cancer plans were prepared using the local protocol with 44Gy + 20Gy boost dose prescriptions. They were evaluated also with the RAIDER protocol quantities [2].
3. Five Gynec plans were prepared using the local protocol with 45 Gy prescription dose and 1.8Gy fraction dose. They were evaluated using the PROKNOW systems protocol instructions [3].
4. Five Anal canal plans were prepared with 45 Gy prescription dose and 1.8Gy fraction dose.

They were evaluated with the National Guidance UK for IMRT in Anal cancer [4] applicable to 50.4Gy prescription dose.

Full double arc VMAT RT plans with 6MV photon energy were generated with the Monaco 5.11 treatment planning system (Elekta, Sweden). The absolute value DVH-s were exported. The protocol-specific constraints, such as Volumes (% or ccm) covered by the given dose of different OAR-s are stored in spreadsheet files (see Appendix). The corresponding values were obtained with an in-house written program. The results were then imported into a spreadsheet program for comparison. The RT plans were administrated using the Synergy (Elekta) linac.

Results

Fig.1. shows the Dose-Volume(%) points of the Rectum, Bladder, and Right Femoral Head in five prostate cancer RT plans with 44+16+14Gy dose prescriptions. The per-protocol values indicate the PASS values of the PROKNOW systems instructions.

Fig.2. shows the Dose-Volume(%) points of the Rectum, Bladder, and Bulbus Penis in prostate cancer RT plans (#1...#5) with 60Gy+14Gy boost dose prescriptions.

Fig.3. shows the Dose-Volume(%) points of the Rectum, and the Volumes(ccm) of the Small Bowel in Bladder cancer treatments of patients. The #1...#5 data were obtained using RAIDER protocol constraints, while points #1local...#5local data represent ones obtained with local protocol.

Fig.4. Shows the Dose-Volume(%) points of the Rectum, Bladder, Bowels, and Femoral Head in Gynec RT plans.

Fig.5. Shows the Dose-Volume(%) points of the Bladder, Bowels, and Femoral Head in Anal canal RT plans and per protocol values.

1. The PROKNOW prostate protocol prescription dose was 60Gy. However, our plans included boosts, and most of plans fulfilled the per-protocol constraints. The Volumes(%) were significantly lower in both 44+16+14Gy and 60+14Gy dose prescriptions. The override of the V(60Gy) values accrued because of the overlap of the structures PTV(60Gy) with the Rectum, and Bladder.
2. Since the protocol RAIDER is applicable for VMAT plans and also for 3D conformal and step-and-shoot IMRT plans, higher doses for the OARs were allowed than in the local protocol. The RAIDER protocol constraints were fulfilled, while the local protocol instructions were partially satisfied.
3. The PROKNOW and the local protocols include similar instruction values. The majority of the Rectum, Bladder, and Bowels Volumes(%) were lower, than the PROKNOW per protocol values, while, ones of the Femoral Heads were not satisfied.
4. The Anal canal RT plans satisfied the per protocol instructions.

Conclusion

Fig.6. Comparison of the different protocol instruction values per OARs

The typical constraints for the Rectum is: Volume covered by 45Gy V(45Gy): 50%, while the largest acceptable value is between 55 and 60Gy. The different protocols' constraints for the Bladder are V(40Gy): 50%, V(50Gy): 5-40%, and the maximal accepted value is between 50 and 60Gy. The PROKNOW prostate protocol constraint for the Bowel is V(40Gy): 17cm, while other protocols allow significantly higher value: 120cm. The PROKNOW Gynec protocol constraint for the Femoral Heads is V(30Gy): 5-15%, while the other protocols allow different values: V(30Gy): 50%, V(40.8Gy): 50%. The maximal accepted dose varies between 40Gy and 50Gy.

References

[1] source: PROKNOW systems, online not available

[2] Hafeez S, Webster A, Hansen VN, *et al.* Protocol for tumour-focused dose-escalated adaptive radiotherapy for the radical treatment of bladder cancer in a multicentre phase II randomised controlled trial (RAIDER): radiotherapy planning and delivery guidance. *BMJ Open* 2020;10:e041005. Doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2020-041005

[3] source: PROKNOW systems, last access: Nov.24.2024

<https://proknowsystems.com/planning/studies/5a94633e1ec00fea64adfa650377efaf1/instructions>

[4] R Muirhead, RA Adams, DC Gilbert *et al.*, National Guidance for IMRT in Anal cancer

<https://www.rcr.ac.uk/our-services/all-our-publications/clinical-oncology-publications/>, last access March 11 2025

Appendix

Summary of the protocol instructions. PP: per protocol, VA: variation acceptable

Local Bladder 44+20/2Gy

					PP	VA	
PTVpelvis	V	4400	cGy	>	95	90	%
PTVwb	D	0.03	ccm	<	7040	7360	cGy
PTVwb	V	6400	cGy	>	95	90	%
Rectum	V	3000	cGy	<	50	55	%
Rectum	V	5000	cGy	<	10	15	%
Femoral Head L	V	4500	cGy	<	50	55	%
Femoral Head L	D	0.03	ccm	<	5000	5500	cGy
Femoral Head R	V	4500	cGy	<	50	55	%
Femoral Head R	D	0.03	ccm	<	5000	5500	cGy
Bowel_Small	V	5000	cGy	<	15	20	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	4500	cGy	<	100	120	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	3000	cGy	<	150	170	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	4000	cGy	<	30	35	%
Bowel_Small	D	0.03	ccm	<	4700	4900	cGy
Bowel_Small	D	0.03	ccm	<	5500	5700	cGy

Raider Bladder

					PP	VA	
PTVboost	D	0.03	ccm	<	7040	7360	%
PTVboost	V	6400	cGy	>	95	90	%
PTVboost	D	0.03	ccm	<	6848	7360	cGy
Rectum	V	3000	cGy	<	80	80	%
Rectum	V	5000	cGy	<	60	60	%
Rectum	V	6000	cGy	<	50	50	%
Rectum	V	6500	cGy	<	30	30	%
Rectum	V	7000	cGy	<	15	15	%
Femoral_Head_R	D	0.03	ccm	<	5000	5500	cGy
Femoral_Head_R	V	5000	cGy	<	50	55	%
Femoral_Head_L	D	0.03	ccm	<	5000	5500	cGy
Femoral_Head_L	V	5000	cGy	<	50	57	%
Bowel_Small	V	4500	cGy	<	116	139	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	5000	cGy	<	104	127	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	5500	cGy	<	91	115	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	6000	cGy	<	73	98	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	6500	cGy	<	23	40	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	7000	cGy	<	0,01	10	ccm
Bowel_Small	D	0.03	ccm	<	4700	4900	cGy

PRKNOW prostate 60Gy

					PP	VA	
PTV6000	D	0,03	ccm	<	6400		cGy
PTV6000	V	6000	cGy	>	95	90	%
Rectum	V	2460	cGy	<	80		%
Rectum	V	3420	cGy	<	70		%
Rectum	V	4080	cGy	<	60		%
Rectum	V	5280	cGy	<	30		%
Rectum	V	5700	cGy	<	15		%
Rectum	V	6000	cGy	<	3		%
Bladder	V	4080	cGy	<	50		%
Bladder	V	4860	cGy	<	25		%
Bladder	V	6000	cGy	<	5		%
Femoral_Head_R	V	4080	cGy	<	50		%
Femoral_Head_R	V	4500	cGy	<	1		%
Femoral_Head_L	V	4080	cGy	<	50		%
Femoral_Head_L	V	4500	cGy	<	1		%
Bowels	V	4080	cGy	<	17		ccm
URETHRABULB	V	4080	cGy	<	50		%
URETHRABULB	V	4860	cGy	<	10		%

Proknow gyne 45Gy

					PP	VA	
PTVpelvis	V	4500	cGy	>	95	90	%
PTVpelvis	D	0,03	ccm	<	4950	5175	cGy
Rectum	V	3000	cGy	<	50	55	%
Rectum	V	5000	cGy	<	10	15	%
Femoral_Head_R	D	0,03	ccm	<	5000	5500	cGy
Femoral_Head_R	V	4500	cGy	<	50	55	%
Femoral_Head_R	V	3000	cGy	<	5	20	%
Femoral_Head_L	D	0,03	ccm	<	5000	5500	cGy
Femoral_Head_L	V	4500	cGy	<	50	57	%
Femoral_Head_L	V	3000	cGy	<	5	20	%
Bowel_Small	V	4300	cGy	<	15	20	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	3900	cGy	<	100	120	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	3400	cGy	<	130	150	ccm
Bowel_Small	V	2600	cGy	<	150	170	ccm
Bowel_Small	D	0,03	ccm	<	4700	4900	cGy
Bladder	V	4500	cGy	<	30	35	%
Bladder	V	5000	cGy	<	20	25	%

Anal canal UK		50,4 Gy		PP		VA	
PTV	D	0,03	ccm	<	5400	5500	cGy
PTV	V	5040	cGy	>	95	90	%
Bladder	V	3500	cGy	<	50		%
Bladder	V	4000	cGy	<	35		%
Bladder	V	5000	cGy	<	5		%
Femoral_Head_R	V	3000	cGy	<	50		%
Femoral_Head_R	V	4000	cGy	<	35		%
Femoral_Head_R	V	5000	cGy	<	5		%
Femoral_Head_L	V	3000	cGy	<	50		%
Femoral_Head_L	V	4000	cGy	<	35		%
Femoral_Head_L	V	5000	cGy	<	5		%
Bowels	D	200	ccm	<	3000	3500	cGy
Bowels	D	150	ccm	<	3500	4000	cGy
Bowels	D	5	ccm	<	5000	5500	cGy
Bowels	D	0,03	ccm	<	5800		cGy
Genitalia	V	2000	cGy	<	50		%
Genitalia	V	3000	cGy	<	35		%
Genitalia	V	4000	cGy	<	5		%